

NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

CORE DEPARTMENT

MSc THESIS

**Supervisor Control in a cyber-physical system for vehicle flow in
the presence of actuators and sensors faults**

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Abstract

In this thesis, the mathematical model of the car flow of the Algra bridge in the Netherlands will be presented. The bridge consists of four traffic lanes, two for vehicles, one for bicycles and one for pedestrians. The mathematical models of the actuators and sensors subsystems with and without the presence of faults will be presented. The overall system model will be developed. All operating and safety specifications will be presented. The specifications will be presented in the desired regular languages. The properties of the desired languages in terms of the overall automaton of the system will be investigated. The possibility of designing a modular supervisory control architecture will be explored.

Keywords: Finite Deterministic Automata, Cyber-Physical systems, Supervisory Control, Actuator Faults, Sensor Faults.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

In this thesis, we present a mathematical model for traffic flow on the Algra Bridge in the Netherlands. The bridge consists of four lanes: two for vehicles, one for bicycles, and one for pedestrians. Mathematical models for the subsystems of actuators and sensors will be developed, both with and without the presence of faults. The overall system model will be synthesized, and all functional and safety specifications will be outlined. These specifications will be expressed in the form of desired regular languages. The properties of these languages will be investigated with respect to the system's global automaton. Additionally, the feasibility of designing a modular supervisory control architecture will be explored.

Cyber-physical systems (CPS) have grown increasingly complex due to rising safety requirements and functional demands. Controllers for such systems have also become more sophisticated (see [1]-[2]). In [2], desired system behavior is formulated as logical propositions, both with and without faults. However, [2] does not address the feasibility of supervisors or deadlock avoidance in the controlled system. The analytical formulation of regular languages corresponding to desired behaviors, along with a control architecture that ensures both specification adherence and deadlock avoidance, remains an open research challenge (see [3]-[4]).

System modeling will employ finite deterministic automata and operations between automata (e.g., parallel composition, as in [1]-[21]). Desired behaviors will be defined as regular languages. The design of the structured modular supervisory control architecture will leverage dynamic supervisors based on these languages. Properties of the languages will be analyzed to derive sufficient conditions for resolving modular control problems ([18]-[57]). Dynamic supervisors ([32]-[57]) will form the basis of the control architecture.

Thesis Structure, in Chapter 2 the mathematical model of the system without faults is presented.

In Chapter 3 the mathematical model of the system with faults is given.

In Chapter 4 the desired system behavior and the respective regular language of the specifications are presented.

In Chapter 5 the design of the supervisors is developed.

CHAPTER 2: MODELING OF THE CYBERPHYSICAL SYSTEM OF THE ALGERA BRIDGE

The I/O (Input/Output) list of the Algera Bridge has been used to design the installation model. The bridge is composed of four distinct types of device models: 14 car traffic lights, 6 traffic control barriers, 1 bridge gate, and 4 ship traffic lights.

2.1 MODELING OF THE TRAFFIC LIGHTS WITHOUT FAULTS

The traffic light consist of an input to activate the signal and an output that serves as a feedback signal. By default, the signal is deactivated, which is also the desired operational (state). The nominal behavior ensures that the sensor activates or deactivates only when the signal is active or inactive, respectively

2.1.1 Mathematical model of the traffic light actuator without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the traffic light actuator [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{TA} = (\mathbb{Q}_{TA}, \mathbb{E}_{TA}, f_{TA}, \mathbb{H}_{TA}, x_{TA,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{TA,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{TA} = \{q_{TA,1}, q_{TA,2}\}$$

The state $q_{TA,1}$ is when the actuator is deactivated (OFF). The state $q_{TA,2}$ is when the actuator is activated (ON).

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{TA} = \{e_{TA,1}, e_{TA,2}\}$$

The event $e_{TA,1}$ is the command to the actuator to activate. The event $e_{TA,2}$ is the command to the actuator to deactivate.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{TA}(q_{TA,1}, e_{TA,1}) = q_{TA,2} \text{ and } f_{TA}(q_{TA,2}, e_{TA,2}) = q_{TA,1}$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{H}_{TA}(q_{TA,1}) = \{e_{TA,1}\}, \text{ and } \mathbb{H}_{TA}(q_{TA,2}) = \{e_{TA,2}\}.$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{TA,0} = q_{TA,1}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{TA,m} = \{q_{TA,1}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{TA,c} = \{e_{TA,1}, e_{TA,2}\}$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{TA,uc} = \emptyset$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{TA}) = \overline{(e_{TA,1}e_{TA,2})^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{TA}) = (e_{TA,1}e_{TA,2})^*.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{TA})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{TA}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: State diagram of the automaton of the traffic light actuator

2.1.2 Mathematical model of the traffic light sensor without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the traffic light sensor [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{TS} = (\mathbb{Q}_{TS}, \mathbb{E}_{TS}, f_{TS}, \mathbb{H}_{TS}, x_{TS,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{TS,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{TS} = \{q_{TS,1}, q_{TS,2}\}$$

The state $q_{TS,1}$ is when the sensor is deactivated (OFF). The state $q_{TS,2}$ is when the sensor is activated (ON).

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{TS} = \{e_{TS,1}, e_{TS,2}\}$$

The event $e_{TS,1}$ is the signal that the sensor is activated. The event $e_{TS,2}$ is the signal that the sensor is deactivated.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{TS}(q_{TS,1}, e_{TS,1}) = q_{TS,2} \text{ and } f_{TS}(q_{TS,2}, e_{TS,2}) = q_{TS,1}$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{H}_{TS}(q_{TS,1}) = \{e_{TS,1}\} \text{ and } \mathbb{H}_{TS}(q_{TS,2}) = \{e_{TS,2}\}.$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{TS,0} = q_{TS,1}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{TS,m} = \{q_{TS,1}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{TS,c} = \emptyset$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{TS,uc} = \{e_{TS,1}, e_{TS,2}\}$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{TS}) = \overline{(e_{TS,1}e_{TS,2})^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{TS}) = (e_{TS,1}e_{TS,2})^*.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{TS})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{TS}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: State diagram of the automaton of the traffic light sensor

2.2 MODELING OF THE TRAFFIC CONTROL BARRIERS WITHOUT FAULTS

2.2.1 Mathematical model of the traffic control barriers actuator without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the traffic control barriers actuator [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{BA} = (\mathbb{Q}_{BA}, \mathbb{E}_{BA}, f_{BA}, \mathbb{H}_{BA}, x_{BA,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{BA,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{BA} = \{q_{BA,1}, q_{BA,2}, q_{BA,3}\}$$

The state $q_{BA,1}$ is when the barrier is not moving (idle). The state $q_{BA,2}$ is when the barrier is moving up. The state $q_{BA,3}$ is when the barrier is moving down.

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{BA} = \{e_{BA,1}, e_{BA,2}, e_{BA,3}\}$$

The event $e_{BA,1}$ is the command to the actuator to move up the barrier. The event $e_{BA,2}$ is the command to the actuator to move down the barrier. The event $e_{BA,3}$ is the command to the actuator to stop.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{BA}(q_{BA,1}, e_{BA,1}) = q_{BA,2}, \quad f_{BA}(q_{BA,1}, e_{BA,2}) = q_{BA,3}$$

$$f_{BA}(q_{BA,2}, e_{BA,3}) = q_{BA,1}$$

$$\text{and } f_{BA}(q_{BA,3}, e_{BA,3}) = q_{BA,1}$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{H}_{BA}(q_{BA,1}) = \{e_{BA,1}, e_{BA,2}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{BA}(q_{BA,2}) = \{e_{BA,3}\}$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{H}_{BA}(q_{BA,3}) = \{e_{BA,3}\}.$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{BA,0} = q_{BA,1}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{BA,m} = \{q_{BA,1}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{BA,c} = \{e_{BA,1}, e_{BA,2}, e_{BA,3}\}$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{BA,uc} = \emptyset$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{BA}) = \overline{(e_{BA,1}e_{BA,3} + e_{BA,2}e_{BA,3})^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{BA}) = (e_{BA,1}e_{BA,3} + e_{BA,2}e_{BA,3})^*.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{BA})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{BA}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: State diagram of the automaton of the traffic barrier actuator

2.2.2 Mathematical model of the traffic barrier sensor without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the traffic barrier sensor [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{BS} = (\mathbb{Q}_{BS}, \mathbb{E}_{BS}, f_{BS}, \mathbb{H}_{BS}, x_{BS,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{BS,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{BS} = \{q_{BS,1}, q_{BS,2}, q_{BS,3}\}$$

The state $q_{BS,1}$ is when the sensor indicates that the barrier is open. The state $q_{BS,2}$ is when the sensor indicates that the barrier is between open and close. The state $q_{BS,3}$ is when the sensor indicates that the barrier is closed.

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{BS} = \{e_{BS,1}, e_{BS,2}, e_{BS,3}, e_{BS,4}\}$$

The event $e_{BS,1}$ is the signal that the barrier is not open. The event $e_{BS,2}$ is the signal that the barrier is open. The event $e_{BS,3}$ is the signal that the barrier is closed. The event $e_{BS,4}$ is the signal that the barrier is not closed.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{BS}(q_{BS,1}, e_{BS,1}) = q_{BS,2},$$

$$f_{BS}(q_{BS,2}, e_{BS,2}) = q_{BS,1}$$

$$f_{BS}(q_{BS,2}, e_{BS,3}) = q_{BS,3} \text{ and } f_{BS}(q_{BS,3}, e_{BS,4}) = q_{BS,2}$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{H}_{BS}(q_{BS,1}) = \{e_{BS,1}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{BS}(q_{BS,2}) = \{e_{BS,2}, e_{BS,3}\}$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{H}_{BS}(q_{BS,3}) = \{e_{BS,4}\} \dots$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{BS,0} = q_{BS,1}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{BS,m} = \{q_{BS,1}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{BS,c} = \emptyset$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{BS,uc} = \{e_{BS,1}, e_{BS,2}, e_{BS,3}, e_{BS,4}\}$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{BS}) = \overline{\left(e_{BS,1} \left(e_{BS,2} + (e_{BS,3} e_{BA,4})^* \right) \right)^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{BS}) = \left(e_{BS,1} \left(e_{BS,2} + (e_{BS,3} e_{BA,4})^* \right) \right)^*.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{BS})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{BS}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: State diagram of the automaton of the traffic barrier sensor

2.3 MODELING OF THE BRIDGE WITHOUT FAULTS

2.3.1 Mathematical model of the bridge actuator without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the bridge actuator [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{DA} = (\mathbb{Q}_{DA}, \mathbb{E}_{DA}, f_{DA}, \mathbb{H}_{DA}, x_{DA,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{DA,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{DA} = \{q_{DA,1}, q_{DA,2}, q_{DA,3}\}$$

The state $q_{DA,1}$ is when the bridge is not moving. The state $q_{DA,2}$ is when the bridge is moving up. The state $q_{DA,3}$ is when the bridge is moving down.

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{DA} = \{e_{DA,1}, e_{DA,2}, e_{DA,3}\}$$

The event $e_{DA,1}$ is the command to the actuator to move up the bridge. The event $e_{DA,2}$ is the command to the actuator to move down the bridge. The event $e_{DA,3}$ is the command to the actuator to stop.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{DA}(q_{DA,1}, e_{DA,1}) = q_{DA,2},$$

$$f_{DA}(q_{DA,1}, e_{DA,2}) = q_{DA,3}$$

$$f_{DA}(q_{DA,2}, e_{DA,3}) = q_{DA,1}$$

$$\text{And } f_{DA}(q_{DA,3}, e_{DA,3}) = q_{DA,1}$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{H}_{DA}(q_{DA,1}) = \{e_{DA,1}, e_{DA,2}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{DA}(q_{DA,2}) = \{e_{DA,3}\}$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{H}_{DA}(q_{DA,3}) = \{e_{DA,3}\}.$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{DA,0} = q_{DA,1}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{DA,m} = \{q_{DA,1}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{DA,c} = \{e_{DA,1}, e_{DA,2}, e_{DA,3}\}$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{DA,uc} = \emptyset$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{DA}) = \overline{(e_{DA,1}e_{DA,3} + e_{DA,2}e_{DA,3})^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{DA}) = (e_{DA,1}e_{DA,3} + e_{DA,2}e_{DA,3})^*.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{DA})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{DA}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: State diagram of the automaton of the bridge actuator

2.3.2 Mathematical model of the bridge sensor without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the bridge sensor [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{DS} = (\mathbb{Q}_{DS}, \mathbb{E}_{DS}, f_{DS}, \mathbb{H}_{DS}, x_{DS,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{DS,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{DS} = \{q_{DS,1}, q_{DS,2}, q_{DS,3}\}$$

The state $q_{DS,1}$ is when the sensor indicates that the bridge is open. The state $q_{DS,2}$ is when the sensor indicates that the bridge is between open and close. The state $q_{DS,3}$ is when the sensor indicates that the bridge is closed.

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{DS} = \{e_{DS,1}, e_{DS,2}, e_{DS,3}, e_{DS,4}\}$$

The event $e_{DS,1}$ is the signal that the bridge is not open. The event $e_{DS,2}$ is the signal that the bridge is open. The event $e_{DS,3}$ is the signal that the bridge is closed. The event $e_{DS,4}$ is the signal that the bridge is not closed.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$\begin{aligned} f_{DS}(q_{DS,1}, e_{DS,1}) &= q_{DS,2}, \\ f_{DS}(q_{DS,2}, e_{DS,2}) &= q_{DS,1} \\ f_{DS}(q_{DS,2}, e_{DS,3}) &= q_{DS,3} \\ \text{and } f_{DS}(q_{DS,3}, e_{DS,4}) &= q_{DS,2} \end{aligned}$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{H}_{DS}(q_{DS,1}) &= \{e_{DS,1}\}, \\ \mathbb{H}_{DS}(q_{DS,2}) &= \{e_{DS,2}, e_{DS,3}\} \\ \text{and } \mathbb{H}_{DS}(q_{DS,3}) &= \{e_{DS,4}\}. \end{aligned}$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{DS,0} = q_{DS,3}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{DS,m} = \{q_{DS,3}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{BS,c} = \emptyset$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{DS,uc} = \{e_{DS,1}, e_{DS,2}, e_{DS,3}, e_{DS,4}\}$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{DS}) = \overline{\left(e_{DS,1} \left(e_{DS,2} + (e_{DS,3} e_{DS,4})^* \right) \right)^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{DS}) = \left(e_{DS,1} \left(e_{DS,2} + (e_{DS,3} e_{DS,4})^* \right) \right)^*.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{DS})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{DS}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: State diagram of the automaton of the bridge sensor

2.4 MODELING OF THE SHIP TRAFFIC LIGHTS WITHOUT FAULTS

2.4.1 Mathematical model of the ship traffic lights actuator without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the ship traffic lights actuator [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{VA} = (\mathbb{Q}_{VA}, \mathbb{E}_{VA}, f_{VA}, \mathbb{H}_{VA}, x_{VA,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{VA,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{VA} = \{q_{VA,1}, q_{VA,2}, q_{VA,3}, q_{VA,4}\}$$

The state $q_{VA,1}$ is when the ship traffic light is in the red aspect. The state $q_{VA,2}$ is when the ship traffic light is in the red-red aspect. The state $q_{VA,3}$ is when the ship traffic light is in the red-green aspect. The state $q_{VA,4}$ is when the ship traffic light is in the green aspect.

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{VA} = \{e_{VA,1}, e_{VA,2}, e_{VA,3}, e_{VA,4}\}$$

The event $e_{VA,1}$ is the command to the actuator to activate the red-red aspect. The event $e_{VA,2}$ is the command to the actuator to activate the red aspect. The event $e_{VA,3}$ is the command to the actuator to activate the red-green aspect. The event $e_{VA,4}$ is the command to the actuator to activate the green aspect.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{VA}(q_{VA,1}, e_{VA,1}) = q_{VA,2},$$

$$f_{VA}(q_{VA,1}, e_{VA,3}) = q_{VA,3},$$

$$f_{VA}(q_{VA,2}, e_{VA,2}) = q_{VA,1},$$

$$f_{VA}(q_{VA,3}, e_{VA,2}) = q_{VA,1},$$

$$f_{VA}(q_{VA,3}, e_{VA,4}) = q_{VA,4}$$

and $f_{VA}(q_{VA,4}, e_{VA,2}) = q_{VA,1}$

The active events set are

$$\mathbb{H}_{VA}(q_{VA,1}) = \{e_{VA,1}, e_{VA,3}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{VA}(q_{VA,2}) = \{e_{VA,2}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{VA}(q_{VA,3}) = \{e_{VA,2}, e_{VA,4}\}$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{H}_{VA}(q_{VA,4}) = \{e_{VA,2}\}.$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{VA,0} = q_{VA,1}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{VA,m} = \{q_{VA,1}, q_{VA,2}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{VA,c} = \{e_{VA,1}, e_{VA,2}, e_{VA,3}, e_{VA,4}\}$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{VA,uc} = \emptyset$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{VA}) = \overline{((e_{VA,1}e_{VA,2})^* e_{VA,3}(e_{VA,1} + e_{VA,4}e_{VA,1}))^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{VA}) = \overline{((e_{VA,1}e_{VA,2})^* e_{VA,3}(e_{VA,1} + e_{VA,4}e_{VA,1}))^*}.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{VA})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{VA}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: State diagram of the automaton of the ship traffic light actuator

2.4.2 Mathematical model of the ship traffic lights sensor without the presence of faults

The mathematical model of the ship traffic light sensor [1] using finite deterministic automata ([5]-[11]) is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{VS} = (\mathbb{Q}_{VS}, \mathbb{E}_{VS}, f_{VS}, \mathbb{H}_{VS}, x_{VS,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{VS,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{VS} = \{q_{VS,1}, q_{VS,2}\}$$

The state $q_{VS,1}$ is when the sensor is activated. The state $q_{VS,2}$ is when the sensor is deactivated.

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{VS} = \{e_{VS,1}, e_{VS,2}\}$$

The event $e_{VS,1}$ is the signal that the sensor is activated. The event $e_{VS,2}$ is the signal that the sensor is deactivated.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{VS}(q_{VS,1}, e_{VS,1}) = q_{VS,2}$$

$$\text{and } f_{VS}(q_{VS,2}, e_{VS,2}) = q_{VS,1}.$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{H}_{VS}(q_{VS,1}) = \{e_{VS,1}\}$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{H}_{VS}(q_{VS,2}) = \{e_{VS,2}\}.$$

The initial state of the automaton is $x_{VS,0} = q_{VS,1}$.

The marked states of the automaton are $\mathbb{Q}_{VS,m} = \{q_{VS,1}\}$.

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{VS,c} = \emptyset$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{VS,uc} = \{e_{VS,1}, e_{VS,2}\}$.

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{VS}) = \overline{(e_{VS,1}e_{VS,2})^*}.$$

The marked behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{VS}) = (e_{VS,1}e_{VS,2})^*.$$

The system avoids entrapment as

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_{VS})} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_{VS}).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: State diagram of the automaton of the ship traffic light sensor

CHAPTER 3: MODELING OF THE CYBERPHYSICAL SYSTEM OF THE ALGERA BRIDGE IN THE PRESENCE OF FAULTS

3.1 MODELING OF THE TRAFFIC LIGHTS WITHOUT FAULTS

The mathematical model of faults is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_F = (\mathbb{Q}_F, \mathbb{E}_F, f_F, \mathbb{H}_F, x_{F,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{F,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_F = \{q_{F,1}, q_{F,2}\}$$

The state $q_{F,1}$ is when no fault has been detected. The state $q_{F,2}$ is when a fault took place.

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_F = \{e_{F,1}, e_{F,2}\}$$

The event $e_{F,1}$ is the signal that a fault has been detected. The event $e_{F,2}$ is the signal that the fault has been repaired.

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_F(q_{F,1}, e_{F,1}) = q_{F,2}$$

$$\text{and } f_F(q_{F,2}, e_{F,2}) = q_{F,1}$$

The active events sets are

$$\mathbb{H}_F(q_{F,1}) = \{e_{F,1}\}$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{H}_F(q_{F,2}) = \{e_{F,2}\}.$$

The initial state is

$$x_{F,0} = q_{F,1}.$$

The marked state is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{F,m} = \{q_{F,1}\}.$$

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{F,c} = \emptyset$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{F,uc} = \{e_{F,1}, e_{F,2}\}.$

The closed behavior of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_F) = \overline{(e_{F,1}e_{F,2})^*}$$

The marked behavior is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_F) = (e_{F,1}e_{F,2})^*$$

The automaton is a nonblocking automaton

$$\overline{\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{G}_F)} = \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{G}_F).$$

The state diagram of the automaton is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: State diagram of the automaton of the faults

3.2 ACTUATORS AND SENSORS MODELS IN THE PRESENCE OF FAULTS

The mathematical models of the systems presented in Chapter 2 in combination with the mathematical model of the fault, compose the mathematical model of the actuators and sensors in the presence of faults. Thus, the models are of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{FTA} = \mathbf{G}_{TA} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{FTS} = \mathbf{G}_{TS} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{FBA} = \mathbf{G}_{BA} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{FBS} = \mathbf{G}_{BS} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{FDA} = \mathbf{G}_{DA} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{FDS} = \mathbf{G}_{DS} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{FVA} = \mathbf{G}_{VA} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{FVS} = \mathbf{G}_{VS} \parallel \mathbf{G}_F$$

Next, the model of the traffic light actuator will be presented. The mathematical model is of the form

$$\mathbf{G}_{FTA} = (\mathbb{Q}_{FTA}, \mathbb{E}_{FTA}, f_{FTA}, \mathbb{H}_{FTA}, x_{FTA,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{FTA,m})$$

The set of states of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{FTA} = \{(q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1}), (q_{TA,1}, q_{F,2}), (q_{TA,2}, q_{F,1}), (q_{TA,2}, q_{F,2})\}$$

The alphabet of the automaton is

$$\mathbb{E}_{FTA} = \{e_{TA,1}, e_{TA,2}, e_{F,1}, e_{F,2}\}$$

The transition functions of the automaton are

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1}), e_{TA,1}) = (q_{TA,2}, q_{F,1}),$$

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1}), e_{F,1}) = (q_{TA,1}, q_{F,2})$$

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,2}, q_{F,1}), e_{TA,2}) = (q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1}),$$

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,2}, q_{F,1}), e_{F,1}) = (q_{TA,2}, q_{F,2})$$

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,1}, q_{F,2}), e_{TA,1}) = (q_{TA,2}, q_{F,2}),$$

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,1}, q_{F,2}), e_{F,2}) = (q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1})$$

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,2}, q_{F,2}), e_{TA,2}) = (q_{TA,1}, q_{F,2}),$$

$$f_{FTA}((q_{TA,2}, q_{F,2}), e_{F,2}) = (q_{TA,2}, q_{F,1})$$

The sets of active events of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{H}_{FTA}((q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1})) = \{e_{TA,1}, e_{F,1}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{FTA}((q_{TA,2}, q_{F,1})) = \{e_{TA,2}, e_{F,1}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{FTA}((q_{TA,1}, q_{F,2})) = \{e_{TA,1}, e_{F,2}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{FTA}((q_{TA,2}, q_{F,2})) = \{e_{TA,2}, e_{F,2}\}.$$

The initial state of the automaton is

$$x_{FTA,0} = (q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1}).$$

The marked states of the automaton are

$$\mathbb{Q}_{FTA,m} = (q_{TA,1}, q_{F,1}).$$

The set of controllable events is $\mathbb{E}_{FTA,c} = \{e_{TA,1}, e_{TA,2}\}$ and the set of uncontrollable events is $\mathbb{E}_{FTA,uc} = \{e_{F,1}, e_{F,2}\}$.

CHAPTER 4: DESIRED BEHAVIOR AND REGULAR LANGUAGES

4.1 DESIRED BEHAVIOR

In [1] a set of rules for proper and safe operation has been proposed where

1. If all the traffic lights are not activated, then the stop signals cannot be activated.
2. If all the stop signals of the traffic lights are not activated, then the entry barriers cannot be closed.
3. If all the entry barriers are not closed, then the exit barriers cannot be closed.
4. If all the barriers are not closed, then the bridge cannot be opened.

4.2 REGULAR LANGUAGES

For each of the above specifications a regular language will be developed

For specification 1 it holds that

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,1,i} = \overline{(e_{TA,i,1}(e_{TA,7,1}, \dots, e_{TA,16,1})^* e_{TA,i,2})^*}; i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,1,i+6} = \overline{(e_{TS,i,1}(e_{TA,7,1}, \dots, e_{TA,16,1})^* e_{TS,i,2})^*}; i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

For specification 2 it holds that

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,2,i} = \overline{(e_{BA,i,1}(e_{TA,7,1}, \dots, e_{TA,16,1})^* e_{BA,i,2})^*}; i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,2,i+6} = \overline{(e_{BS,i,1}(e_{TA,7,1}, \dots, e_{TA,16,1})^* e_{BS,i,2})^*}; i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

For specification 3 it holds that

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,3,1} = \overline{(e_{BA,1,1}(e_{BA,2,1}, e_{BA,3,1})^* e_{BA,1,2})^*}$$

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,3,2} = \overline{(e_{BS,1,1}(e_{BA,2,1}, e_{BA,3,1})^* e_{BS,1,2})^*}$$

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,3,3} = \overline{(e_{BA,4,1}(e_{BA,2,1}, e_{BA,3,1})^* e_{BA,4,2})^*}$$

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,3,4} = \overline{(e_{BS,4,1}(e_{BA,2,1}, e_{BA,3,1})^* e_{BS,4,2})^*}$$

For specification 4 it holds that

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,4,i} = \overline{(e_{BA,i,1}(e_{DA,1})^* e_{BA,i,2})^*}; i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

$$\mathbb{K}_{D,4,i+6} = \overline{(e_{BS,i,1}(e_{DA,1})^* e_{BS,i,2})^*}; i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

The remaining languages are constructed in a similar way.

CHAPTER 5: SUPERVISOR DESIGN

5.1 SUPERVISOR OF LANGUAGE $\mathbb{K}_{D,1}$

For regular language $\mathbb{K}_{D,1}$ the automaton of the supervisor is of the form ([5]-[11])

$$\mathbf{S}_1 = (\mathbb{Q}_{S,1}, \mathbb{E}_{S,1}, f_{S,1}, \mathbb{H}_{S,1}, x_{S,1,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{S,1,m})$$

The set of the states is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{S,1} = \{q_{S,1,1}, q_{S,1,2}\}$$

The alphabet of the supervisor is

$$\mathbb{E}_{S,1} = \{e_{TA,i,1}, e_{TA,i,2}, e_{TA,7,2}, \dots, e_{TA,16,2}\}$$

The initial state is

$$x_{S,1,0} = q_{S,1,1}.$$

The set of the marked states is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{S,1,m} = \mathbb{Q}_{S,1}.$$

The transition functions are

$$\begin{aligned} f_{S,1}(q_{S,1,1}, e_{TA,i,1}) &= q_{S,1,2}, \\ f_{S,1}(q_{S,1,2}, e) &= q_{S,1,2}; e \in \{e_{TA,7,2}, \dots, e_{TA,16,2}\}, \\ f_{S,1}(q_{S,1,2}, e_{TA,i,2}) &= q_{S,1,1} \end{aligned}$$

The set of the active events per state is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{H}_{S,1}(q_{S,1,1}) &= \{e_{TA,i,1}\}, \\ \mathbb{H}_{S,1}(q_{S,1,2}) &= \{e_{TA,i,2}, e_{TA,7,2}, \dots, e_{TA,16,2}\} \end{aligned}$$

The closed behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{S}_1) = \mathbb{K}_{D,1,i}$$

Finally, the marked behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(\mathbf{S}_1) = \mathbb{K}_{D,1,i}$$

The state diagram of the automaton is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10: State diagram of the automaton of supervisor \mathbf{S}_1

5.2 SUPERVISOR OF LANGUAGE $\mathbb{K}_{D,2}$

For regular language $\mathbb{K}_{D,2}$ the automaton of the supervisor is of the form ([5]-[11])

$$\mathbf{S}_2 = (\mathbb{Q}_{S,2}, \mathbb{E}_{S,2}, f_{S,2}, \mathbb{H}_{S,2}, x_{S,2,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{S,2,m})$$

The set of the states is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{S,2} = \{q_{S,2,1}, q_{S,2,2}\}$$

The alphabet of the supervisor is

$$\mathbb{E}_{S,2} = \{e_{BA,i,1}, e_{TA,7,1}, \dots, e_{TA,16,1}, e_{BA,i,2}\}$$

The initial state is

$$x_{S,2,0} = q_{S,2,1}$$

The set of the marked states is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{S,2,m} = \mathbb{Q}_{S,2}$$

The transition functions are

$$f_{S,2}(q_{S,2,1}, e_{BA,i,1}) = q_{S,2,2},$$

$$f_{S,2}(q_{S,2,2}, e) = q_{S,2,2}; e \in \{e_{TA,7,1}, \dots, e_{TA,16,1}\},$$

$$f_{S,2}(q_{S,2,2}, e_{BA,i,2}) = q_{S,2,1}$$

The set of the active events per state is

$$\mathbb{H}_{S,2}(q_{S,2,1}) = \{e_{BA,i,1}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{S,2}(q_{S,2,2}) = \{e_{TA,7,1}, \dots, e_{TA,16,1}, e_{BA,i,2}\}.$$

The closed behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(S_2) = \mathbb{K}_{D,2,i}$$

Finally, the marked behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(S_2) = \mathbb{K}_{D,2,i}$$

The state diagram of the automaton is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11: State diagram of the automaton of supervisor S_2

5.3 SUPERVISOR OF LANGUAGE $\mathbb{K}_{D,3}$

For regular language $\mathbb{K}_{D,3}$ the automaton of the supervisor is of the form ([5]-[11])

$$S_3 = (\mathbb{Q}_{S,3}, \mathbb{E}_{S,3}, f_{S,3}, \mathbb{H}_{S,3}, x_{S,3,0}, \mathbb{Q}_{S,3,m})$$

The set of the states is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{S,3} = \{q_{S,3,1}, q_{S,3,2}\}$$

The alphabet of the supervisor is

$$\mathbb{E}_{S,3} = \{e_{BA,1,1}, e_{BA,2,1}, e_{BA,3,1}, e_{BA,1,2}\}$$

The initial state is

$$x_{S,3,0} = q_{S,3,1}.$$

The set of the marked states is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{S,3,m} = \mathbb{Q}_{S,3}.$$

The transition functions are

$$f_{S,3}(q_{S,3,1}, e_{BA,1,1}) = q_{S,3,2},$$

$$f_{S,3}(q_{S,3,2}, e_{BA,2,1}) = q_{S,3,2},$$

$$f_{S,3}(q_{S,3,2}, e_{BA,3,1}) = q_{S,3,2}$$

$$f_{S,3}(q_{S,3,2}, e_{BA,1,2}) = q_{S,3,1}$$

The set of the active events per state is

$$\mathbb{H}_{S,3}(q_{S,3,1}) = \{e_{BA,1,1}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{S,3}(q_{S,3,2}) = \{e_{BA,2,1}, e_{BA,3,1}, e_{BA,1,2}\}.$$

The closed behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(S_3) = \mathbb{K}_{D,3,i}$$

Finally, the marked behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(S_3) = \mathbb{K}_{D,3,i}$$

The state diagram of the automaton is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: State diagram of the automaton of supervisor S_3

5.4 SUPERVISOR OF LANGUAGE $\mathbb{K}_{D,4}$

For regular language $\mathbb{K}_{D,4}$ the automaton of the supervisor is of the form ([5]-[11])

$$S_4 = (Q_{S,4}, \mathbb{E}_{S,4}, f_{S,4}, \mathbb{H}_{S,4}, x_{S,4,0}, Q_{S,4,m})$$

The set of the states is

$$Q_{S,4} = \{q_{S,4,1}, q_{S,4,2}\}$$

The alphabet of the supervisor is

$$\mathbb{E}_{S,4} = \{e_{BA,i,1}, e_{DA,1}, e_{BA,i,2}\}$$

The initial state is

$$x_{S,4,0} = q_{S,4,1}.$$

The set of the marked states is

$$\mathbb{Q}_{S,4,m} = \mathbb{Q}_{S,4}.$$

The transition functions are

$$f_{S,4}(q_{S,4,1}, e_{BA,i,1}) = q_{S,4,2},$$

$$f_{S,4}(q_{S,4,2}, e_{DA,1}) = q_{S,4,2},$$

$$\text{and } f_{S,4}(q_{S,4,2}, e_{BA,i,2}) = q_{S,4,1}$$

The set of the active events per state is

$$\mathbb{H}_{S,4}(q_{S,4,1}) = \{e_{BA,i,1}\},$$

$$\mathbb{H}_{S,4}(q_{S,4,2}) = \{e_{DA,1}, e_{BA,i,2}\}.$$

The closed behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}(S_4) = \mathbb{K}_{D,4}$$

Finally, the marked behavior of the supervisor automaton is

$$\mathbb{L}_m(S_4) = \mathbb{K}_{D,4}$$

The state diagram of the automaton is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13: State diagram of the automaton of supervisor S_4

The rest of the supervisors can be developed in a similar way.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSIONS

In this thesis, the mathematical model of the traffic flow of the Algera Bridge in the Netherlands was presented. The bridge consists of four lanes, two for vehicles, one for bicycles and one for pedestrians. The mathematical models of the actuator and sensor subsystems with and without the presence of errors were presented. The overall system model was developed. All operational and safety specifications were presented. The specifications were presented in the form of desired regular languages. A modular supervisory control architecture was designed.

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